

A REGIONAL BIOLOGICAL COLLECTION FOR THE STUDY OF AMPHIBIANS AND REPTILES IN SINALOA, MEXICO

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Scientific collections play a fundamental role in obtaining accurate data and enrich our understanding of biodiversity. This involves the systematic collection of biological specimens, such as plants, animals, fungi, and microorganisms, as well as associated data such as location, date, and environmental characteristics (Simmons, 1987). These activities contribute significantly to taxonomic research, environmental monitoring, the creation of historical records, and other essential aspects in various scientific disciplines (Rohwer et al., 2022; Nachman et al., 2023).

In the Mexican context, at the beginning of the 20th century, the tradition of developing Natural History Museums had faded. It was thanks to the interest and efforts of Mexican biologists who established collections at a personal level, which were later institutionalized (Casas-Andreu et al., 1991). Regionally, scientific collections play a key role by constituting a detailed floristic and faunistic inventory of a specific geographical area. In addition to providing information on distribution patterns and biocultural aspects, these collections are essential for species management and conservation (Reyes-Castillo, 1980; Casas-Andreu et al., 1991). They also play a crucial role in training specialized human resources, such as taxonomists, especially in countries like Mexico, where most research has been conducted by foreigners due to the majority of specimens being found in other countries (Reyes-Castillo, 1980).

The state of Sinaloa, located in northwest Mexico, currently hosts a total of 166 species of amphibians and reptiles (Uetz et al., 2023; Frost, 2024), thanks to its rich biota generated by its geographical location. This diversity combines species from the northern deserts, the tropical lowlands of the south, and the temperate environments of the western slopes of the Sierra Madre Occidental (Lemos-Espinal & Smith, 2020). With an area of 58,092 km² and elevations reaching up to 2,779 meters above sea level, Sinaloa also borders the Gulf of California and the Pacific Ocean to the west, with its coastline extensively divided into small islands and strips of land parallel to the mainland where at least ten major rivers drain (Hardy & McDiarmmid, 1969).

Therefore, the state of Sinaloa is of great biological interest due to pronounced seasonal variations, ecosystem diversity, and the existence of the Mexican Transition Zone, which intersects within the state (Serrano et al., 2014; López-García & Morrone, 2023).

Although this region has been considered one of the best understood in terms of its herpetofaunal diversity due to previous studies conducted in the mid-20th century (Flores-Villela et al., 2004), it is necessary to carry out recent explorations, especially in high elevation areas, which remain scarce due to accessibility difficulties and need to be extensively augmented. Here, I present the rationale for proposing the establishment of a biological collection primarily focused on the study of amphibians and reptiles in Sinaloa. The establishment of a herpetological collection in Sinaloa represents a unique opportunity to strengthen scientific research, education, promote collaboration with other researchers in the country as well as abroad, and the conservation of biodiversity in the region.

The coastal plain of Sinaloa was first explored by European naturalists in the early 19th century (Hardy & McDiarmid, 1969). The port of Mazatlán served as a point of embarkation for specimens from Sinaloa and other areas of northwest Mexico (collections made by Ferdinand Deppe in the early 1800s; Wagler, 1830; Gray, 1831, 1855; Weigmann, 1834; Peters, 1867; Jan, 1863; Fischer; 1883). Subsequently, multiple herpetologists who explored Sinaloa in the early decades of the 20th century made small scientific collections of amphibians and reptiles in the municipalities of Culiacán and Mazatlán; these specimens were later sent to National Museums in the United States and Europe (Fig. 1 and Appendix 1).

Starting in 1936, several works on the herpetofauna of Sinaloa emerged, addressing topics such as distribution, ecology, natural history, and taxonomy (Taylor, 1936; Martin del Campo, 1941; Smith & Van Gelder, 1955; Lewis & Johnson, 1956; Duellman, 1957; Fugler & Dixon, 1961; Campbell & Simmons, 1962; Scott, 1962). The completion of major highways in 1950 facilitated herpetological exploration in regions such as Los Mochis, Guasave, Culiacán, and Mazatlán (Hardy & McDiarmid, 1969). During the 1960s and 1970s, Laurence M. Hardy and Roy W. McDiarmid conducted exhaustive research in Sinaloa, significantly contributing to the herpetofaunal knowledge of Mexico (Hardy & McDiarmid, 1969; McDiarmid et al., 1976). Their studies highlighted ecological aspects, natural history, behavior, physiology, and distribution, in addition to providing detailed morphological descriptions of the region's species. They also emphasized the biogeographical importance of Sinaloa, thus making the region one of the best-studied thanks to their research (Flores-Villela et al., 2004).

In 1984, Robert G. Webb studied the patterns of amphibian and reptile diversity along the Mazatlán-Durango highway (Webb, 1984), although his main focus was the state of Durango, building upon the previous work of Hardy and McDiarmid (1969) in Sinaloa. However, from the 1970s until 2020, scientific research and collections of amphibians and reptiles in Sinaloa drastically declined, possibly due to increasing social conflicts in the region and the absence of local researchers interested in this group (Sarukhán & García-Méndez, 2003; Flores-Villela et al., 2004; Castro-Bastidas & Serrano, 2022). During this period, studies on the state's herpetofauna were limited to species lists (Table 1).

In recent years, there has been a resurgence of local interest in studying the amphibians and reptiles of Sinaloa, with research spanning species diversity, distribution,

behavior, diet, parasites, diseases, malformations, reproduction, and ecology (Saucedo et al., 2019; Loc-Barragán et al., 2020; Uriarte-Garzón et al., 2020; Castro-Bastidas, 2022ab; Castro-Bastidas et al., 2022; Castro-Bastidas & Serrano, 2022; Lara-Reséndiz & Jacobo-González, 2022; Jacobo-González & Castro-Bastidas, 2022; Morales-Lugo et al., 2022; Castro-Bastidas et al., 2023; Aguirre-Zazueta et al., 2023a; Gamez-Duarte et al., 2023; Isaak-Delgado et al., 2023; Jacobo-González et al., 2023; Payan-Cazares et al., 2023; Castro-Bastidas, 2024). Despite the increasing use of citizen science to study the state's diversity (Castro-Bastidas & Serrano, 2022), limitations persist in obtaining precise data due to the lack of guidance from specialized researchers. Genetic, morphological, and taxonomic studies are also scarce (Loc-Barragán et al., 2020; Devitt et al., 2023), and difficulty in accessing certain regions still persists due to social conflicts (Hernández-Salinas et al., 2023), a factor contributing to this information gap.

The absence of scientific collections by both national and foreign researchers has created a bias in the knowledge of the current status of Sinaloa's herpetofauna. Although new species of amphibians and reptiles are described annually at the national level (Ramírez-Bautista et al., 2023), species present in Sinaloa that are described or examined in these studies often remain doubtful or undescribed (Grünwald et al., 2018; Jameson et al., 2022). The arguments for these cases stem from the examination of old specimens, collected only once or from a single locality, lacking genetic data, and no additional collections are made. Below are some examples of these cases:

Craugastor cf. hobartsmithi. Jameson et al. (2022) described six new species of frogs in the genus *Craugastor* in Mexico, mentioning that *Craugastor pygmaeus* had been confused with *C. hobartsmithi* in Jalisco, Nayarit, and Sinaloa. Therefore, the authors limited the distribution of *C. pygmaeus* to the southern part of the country, while individuals from the northwestern coast, where the species had been confused, were referred to as *C. cf. hobartsmithi* pending further research (Fig. 2A). It is worth noting that in this study, no specimens from Sinaloa were examined or collected. Additionally, individuals of *C. pygmaeus*, like those of *C. hobartsmithi* in Sinaloa, have not been recorded for years (Castro-Bastidas & Serrano, 2022). Specific expeditions to search for individuals of *C. cf. hobartsmithi* in Sinaloa are necessary to determine their conservation status, and

the collection of specimens would contribute to clarifying their taxonomic identity in future studies.

Sarcohyla hapsa. Only one individual of this species has been collected in southern Sinaloa, and it has not been recollected for over 50 years (Castro-Bastidas & Serrano, 2022). Individuals of *S. bistincta*, distributed from the Sierra Madre Occidental and Trans-Mexican Volcanic Belt to Jalisco, were assigned to the new species *S. hapsa* described by Campbell et al. (2018); on the other hand, *S. bistincta* (previously registered in Sinaloa) was restricted to central and southwestern Mexico. In the same year, Zarza et al. (2018) discussed *Sarcohyla* lineages and cautioned that additional sampling is required before naming species. Finally, Kaplan and Aguilar (2020) mentioned that the foundations used by Campbell et al. (2018)

were solely based on morphology and distribution of type specimens without conducting additional collections, and they did not describe in their paper which characteristics they considered to separate the species, suggesting that a phylogenetic analysis is necessary to support the proposal of new species within the group. In the description of *S. hapsa*, specimens from Sinaloa were not examined, so not only expeditions to search for individuals of the species would help understand its conservation status, but also collecting specimens would complement subsequent systematic studies.

Lithobates cora. Recently, new species were described for the Ranidae Family on the Pacific coast of Mexico by Pérez-Ramos and Luja-Molina (2023) based on morphological characteristics of specimens collected in this region, and previously described genetic bases proposed this species. The authors determined that populations of *L. forreri* from the northern zone of the Mexican Pacific coast differ from those in the southern part of the country. Morphological variability in the *Lithobates* genus is widely recognized (Hillis et al., 1983; Zaldivar et al., 2004), and this study examined few specimens from Nayarit and only one from Sinaloa. Therefore, it is challenging to determine the real distribution of this species. Additional collections and updated genetic data are suggested to support the presence of this species in Sinaloa.

Crotalus molossus. It has been suggested that *C. basiliscus* and *C. molossus* are sympatric species showing intergradation between southern Sonora and northern Sinaloa (Klauber, 1952;

Hardy & McDiarmid, 1969). Although attempts have been made to describe the distribution range of both species using genetic studies (Muñoz-Mora et al., 2022), no additional collections have been made to determine if there is actual overlap in the distribution ranges of both species. Greater scientific exploration is required in the interior of Sinaloa to understand more ecological aspects of the species. Additionally, individuals found from these species should be examined to elucidate their taxonomic determination.

***Leptodeira* spp.** Lemos-Espinal and Smith (2020) did not include *Leptodeira septentrionalis* in their list of Sinaloa's herpetofauna, probably because Barrio-Amorós (2019) elevated *L. septentrionalis polysticta* to species level, thus considering individuals from western Mexico as *L. polysticta* until then (Aguirre-Zazueta et al., 2023a). However, Barrio-Amorós (2019) did not examine specimens in his study but compiled a literature review to organize the group's systematics. Subsequently, Costa et al. (2022) conducted a phylogenetic study of the *Leptodeira* genus, concluding that their study does not support the elevation of *L. polysticta* to species level and argued that maintaining the subspecies level for both morphotypes represents a more conservative approach. In Sinaloa, four species belonging to this group are recorded: *L. maculata*, *L. punctata*, *L. septentrionalis*, and *L. splendida* (Jacobogonzález et al., 2023; Castro-Bastidas et al., 2024). Additionally, descriptions of this group have not been made in Sinaloa since Hardy and McDiarmid (1969). It is suggested that in future systematic studies, historical collections of these snake

species be examined or, if necessary, additional collections be made.

Thamnophis eques. There are historical records of *T. eques* from Sinaloa in the municipalities of Concordia, El Rosario, and Escuinapa, according to GBIF (2024) (Fig. 2B). However, Lemos-Espinal and Smith (2020) did not include

this species in their checklist nor did they offer arguments for its exclusion. Since *T. eques* is morphologically similar to *T. cyrtopsis*, they can be easily confused. It is likely that *T. eques* is found in the northern Sierra of Sinaloa, so collecting individuals of these species or similar cases would help in their correct identification.

The confluence of the Mexican Transition Zone promotes a composition of fauna and flora of both Nearctic and Neotropical origin in Sinaloa, which, combined with the surrounding ecosystems, likely influences the morphological variability of many species in the region (McDiarmid et al., 1976; Bezy et al., 2017; Castro-Bastidas et al., 2024). Therefore, conducting specimen collections of amphibians and reptiles in this region of Sinaloa could be important for better understanding the biological diversity and evolutionary processes occurring in this unique ecosystem.

On the other hand, Lemos-Espinal and Smith (2020) included species in their checklist whose presence is inferred based on their distribution in neighboring states, without specimen collection or observations with photographic evidence for Sinaloa, such as *Anaxyrus mexicanus*, *Isthmura sierraoccidentalis*, and *Lampropeltis greeri* (Fig. 3; Serrano et al., 2006; Enderson et al., 2009). Additionally, the absence of scientific explorations for over five decades has left three amphibian species and 19 reptile species in need of verification to clarify their conservation status (Castro-Bastidas & Serrano, 2022; Aguirre-Zazueta et al., 2023b). Therefore, the establishment of a biological collection focused on the study of amphibians and reptiles would facilitate the accession of such specimens, primarily those from the Sierra de Sinaloa, and complement morphological and genetic studies that could be essential for better understanding the identity and conservation of these species.

In the local academic sphere, the Laboratorio de Zoología of the Faculty de Biología at the Universidad Autónoma de Sinaloa (Fig. 4A) only has a few amphibian and reptile species for teaching purposes (Table 2). However, these specimens are deteriorating and lack maintenance, requiring urgent restoration. In contrast, the Laboratorio de Ictiología y Biodiversidad at the Centro de Investigación en Alimentación y Desarrollo (CIAD A.C.) Unidad Mazatlán (Fig. 4B) has a small collection mainly dedicated to the study of fish. This laboratory still contains unexamined specimens of amphibians and reptiles (pers. comm. Marcela Ruiz Guerrero) deposited by herpetologist Albert Maurits Van der Heiden† as a result of a faunal inventory of the Cacaxtla Plateau Protected Natural Area. It is noteworthy that most of these specimens were sent by Van der Heiden to the Zoology Museum of the National Autonomous University of Mexico (MZFC) for processing (Table 2). Although these institutions possess specimens of amphibians and reptiles from Sinaloa, there is no collection in the state specifically dedicated to amphibians and reptiles to support herpetological research.

The lack of a herpetological collection in Sinaloa constrains both the understanding of its diversity and the academic training of future local herpetologists. In my recent experience as a herpetology student, I have had to conduct detailed examinations of specimens in the field where access to the internet for guide consultation may be limited. While photographs have aided in species identification through external support for verification, sometimes it is necessary to resort to additional methods such as physical sampling, particularly when morphologically similar species coexist in a specific area.

Establishing a herpetological collection in Sinaloa would be essential for improving the understanding of regional biodiversity and would facilitate collaboration among local and national researchers. Conversely, depositing specimens in collections elsewhere in the country would limit easy access to them by local researchers. Maintaining these samples in local collections ensures more efficient and productive access for students interested in this discipline.

It is crucial to emphasize that establishing and caring for a scientific collection entails significant short- and long-term responsibility on the part of the institution entrusted with its custody (Casas-Andreu et al., 1991). Additionally, it is essential for the curator to have a solid theoretical foundation and to be fully aware of the limitations and potentialities of systematic methods currently available. On the other hand, the provision of adequate infrastructure is necessary because it not only demands the conservation of specimens (Simmons, 1987) but also tissue samples, preferably through the use of ultra-freezers (Pisani & Villa, 1974). Therefore, it is also important to allocate resources for preservation material for the samples.

Likewise, this poses a new challenge regarding the new generations, who show greater concern for animal welfare and their value in the ecosystem. This attitude can also limit scientific research by reducing the availability of specimens for scientific collections (Rohwer et al., 2022; Nachman et al., 2023). It is crucial to find ethical alternatives for obtaining samples and promote education about the importance of scientific collections in biodiversity research and conservation (Casas-Andreu et al., 1991).

Therefore, the proposal to establish a scientific collection in Sinaloa is acceptable, but the establishment of herpetological collections in Sinaloa must have clear objectives, formality, bioethical treatment to avoid biological deterioration in the locations where specimen collection takes place, and responsibility from the curators in charge, as well as institutional support to ensure the sustainability and success of this initiative.

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